

Notes for Several Formulas.

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Abstract

The paper covers several formulas that I've written down the February 18, 2026, for reusability purposes.

1 DEFINITIONS

We assume these definitions are valid within their conditions:

1.1 DEFINITION OF $L(t) \in \mathbb{R}$

We define:

$$L(b, a) := \int_a^b X(u, n) \cdot du, \quad n := b - a, \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}^{0+}, \quad X(t, p) := \sum_{k=1}^p \frac{t}{p} \cdot kt, \quad p \geq 1, \quad p \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \quad (1)$$

Where $\forall t \in \mathbb{R}, t > 1$.

1.2 DEFINITION OF $W(t, a, b) \in \mathbb{R}$

We define:

$$W(b, a) := L(b, a) \cdot \left(\sum_{k=a}^b L(b, k) \right) + C_{rem}, \quad k \neq b, \quad \forall C_{rem} \in \mathbb{R}, \quad C > 0 \quad (2)$$

Where $\forall t \in \mathbb{R}, t > 0$ and C_{rem} is a remainder constant.

1.3 DEFINITION OF $N_{sum}(t, a, b) \in \mathbb{R}$

We define:

$$N_{sum}(b, a, p, n) := \sqrt{L(b, a)_n^p} \quad (3)$$

If and only if $n_{min} < n < n_{max}$, $n_{min} > 0$.